

**POLICY PATHWAYS TO SUSTAINABILITY: A
COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF RENEWABLE ENERGY
PROGRESS IN INDIA AND SAUDI ARABIA**

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Abstract:

Since the beginning of the Industrial Revolution, the Earth's average temperature has increased by just over 1 degree Celsius (about 2 degrees Fahrenheit). Accurate records started in 1880, and it has gone by an average of 0.07 degrees Celsius (about .13 degrees Fahrenheit) every ten years. But since 1981, the rate of growth has gone up by more than twice as much. In the last forty years, the annual global temperature has gone up by 0.18 degrees Celsius (about 0.32 degrees Fahrenheit). The average temperature in India has also increased by about 0.7 °C. Experts have concluded that India would be one of the most severely affected countries by Climate Change in terms of natural disasters, economic slowdown, health, poverty, migration, food and water crises, etc. is a challenge for Indian policymakers to make effective policies to combat climate change in the present and future. On June 30, 2008, the Indian government announced its National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC), which is made up of eight distinct National Missions. Another is the Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDC) India submitted to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) on October 2, 2015, which outlines the nation's goals for addressing climate change. India announced the latest goal, intending to achieve net-zero status by 2070. India's climate policy, for the first time ever, included a target date for reaching carbon neutrality. As a leading global oil producer, Saudi Arabia at the decisive level recognises its share of responsibility in advancing the fight against the climate crisis. It's a challenge for

policymakers to find reliable and cheap energy sources for greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Therefore, Saudi Arabia wants to reach Net Zero by 2060. The event fits in with the larger goals of Vision 2030, which are to speed up the energy transition, reach goals for sustainability, and start a new wave of investment. This paper critically examines the climate change program and policies of both Saudi Arabia and India, encompassing current trends, achievements, future plans, and potential outcomes. Additionally, it analyses the existing trends and advancements in renewable energy in both countries, revealing a notable disparity between envisioned plans and actual development.

Keyword: India, Saudi Arabia, Climate Change, Policy Responses, Net-Zero Goals, Renewable Energy Progress, Disparities in Implementation.

1. Introduction

The issue of climate change occurring on a global scale has already become a problem. Because of growing human emissions of heat-trapping greenhouse gases, the climate of the Earth is changing, and these changes are already having a significant impact on the environment. Some examples of this include a speedier melting of glaciers and ice sheets, an earlier breakup of ice in lakes and rivers, shifting ranges of plants and animals, and an earlier flowering of flowers and leaves. (*Climate Change Evidence: How Do We Know?*, n.d.) Repercussions of global climate change have been expected by scientists for a long time, and they include the melting of sea ice, a more rapid rise in sea level, and heat waves that last longer and are more severe. (*Home*, n.d.)

Scientists are anticipating that the current trend of rising global temperatures, which is mostly attributable to the emission of greenhouse gases as a result of human activity, will continue for a considerable amount of time. The way in which mankind chooses to go into the future will determine how severe the repercussions of climate change will be. Our planet's climate will be adversely affected by intensified emissions of greenhouse gases, which will have far-reaching and disastrous impacts. However, the severity of these consequences will be determined by the amount of carbon dioxide humans put into the atmosphere. As a result, if we are successful in lowering emissions, we may be able to lessen the severity of some of the adverse effects. (Jackson, n.d.)

World economies utilise fossil fuels for industrialisation and urbanisation and to increase the standard of living, which promotes global warming and pollution. Recent high carbon emissions require mitigation strategies to balance greenhouse gas levels. Renewable energy offers alternatives to fossil fuels. Most renewable energy sources are sustainable and release little carbon, which explains their appeal. The last several years have witnessed fast development in renewable energy due to falling solar and wind power costs.(IEA, 2017)

According to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), which was published in 2021, human activities have contributed to an increase in global temperature of approximately 1.1 degrees Celsius (2 degrees Fahrenheit) since the beginning of the Industrial Revolution (starting in 1750). It is anticipated that the Earth's average temperature would rise by at least 1.5 degrees Celsius over the next few decades (about 3 degrees F). These alterations will have an effect on every single part of the world.(Change, 2023)

The average temperature in India has also increased by about 0.7 °C. Experts have concluded that India would be one of the most severely affected countries by Climate Change in terms of natural disasters, economic slowdown, health, poverty, migration, food and water crises, etc. Child stunting in India is anticipated to rise by 35 per cent by 2050 owing to climate change. Climate change has made tribal people uncomfortable, raised their cost of living, and put their existence in danger. Under a 4°C warming scenario, it is anticipated that the west coast and southern India will change to new, hot climate regimes that will be uninhabitable. Droughts are anticipated to become more common in certain regions, particularly in north-western India, Jharkhand, Orissa, and Chhattisgarh. In the 2040s, crop yields are projected to decline dramatically due to high temperatures. Till today, 15% of India's groundwater supplies are already at or over capacity. In the 2050s, if global warming reaches 2°C, the country will have to import more than double as much. Both Kolkata and Mumbai, highly populated cities, will disappear due to the rise of the sea level. (Krishnan et al., 2020)

Although West Asia is home to vast natural resources, progress in renewable energy has been painfully sluggish. Iran had the most significant proportion of RE expansion, followed by Israel.(Publications,

2023) Regarding renewable energy development, Saudi Arabia is attempting to catch up to its fellow Arab neighbours. At the beginning of the year 2021, Energy Minister Prince Abdul Aziz bin Salman said that the nation intends to issue new bids for generating 15,000 MWs of power capacity using renewable energy projects in 2022 and the following year. (BravoSolution, n.d.) Furthermore, according to the General Authority of Statistics of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, the government intends to create an enormous 15,1 TWh of renewable energy by the order 2024. There are now 13 projects with a total capacity of more than 4,800 megawatts under the National Renewable Energy Program. As solar irradiation in Saudi Arabia is relatively high, more than ninety per cent of the renewable energy is derived from solar power, with the remainder coming from wind farms. So Saudi Arabia is switching to renewable energy since it offers a dependable, sustainable energy supply to sustain economic growth. KSA has made significant pledges in recent years to boost the usage of renewable energy sources, including solar and wind power. New laws and incentives have been taken to encourage the adoption of sustainable practices and clean technology across several industries to support these initiatives. Mohammed bin Salman, the crown prince of KSA, has stated that the country would produce 50 per cent of its energy from the renewable sector by 2030 and will plant 10 billion trees over the next decade. (*The Official Saudi Press Agency*, n.d.) (Government-affiliated Saudi Press Agency) Crown Prince Mohammad Bin Salman stated on 28 March-

"As a leading global oil producer, the Kingdom fully recognises its share of responsibility in advancing the fight against the climate crisis. Just as the Kingdom underpinned energy markets during the oil and gas era, it is going to become a global leader in forging a greener world." (*Environment & Nature*, n.d.)

2. Methodology

The main objective of this study is to examine and investigate Policy Pathways of Renewable Energy Progress in India and Saudi Arabia; additionally, it tracks the development of this strategy and throws insight into the elements that have contributed to its failure.

Bhujanga Rao defines research methodology as "an appropriate method or methods for an exhaustive and detailed investigative study of the problem of research". This study falls under the category of analytical

research, in which the researcher uses the information at hand to critically evaluate the chosen research problem. In this work, documentary analysis is used. The analysis of documents helps to assess and investigate the implementation of renewable energy policies in Saudi Arabia and India, as well as the connections between policy and practice. Prior beliefs that document analysis is crucial in the social sciences because documents can catalyse social interaction in addition to containing textual information that can be used to analyse social phenomena. Document analysis therefore can provide insight into the environment in which a given policy develops as well as how that policy affects and reflects societal change. Documents from the governments of Saudi Arabia and India and the World Bank, United Nations, and World Economic Forum serve as sources for this research.

3. Policies and Programmes of India

On June 30, 2008, India's government issued its NAPCC (National Action Plan on Climate Change). In this strategy, Eight National Missions are outlined to address the issue of global warming. They consist:

- ✚ National Solar Mission
- ✚ National Mission for Enhanced Energy Efficiency
- ✚ National Mission on Sustainable Habitat
- ✚ National Water Mission
- ✚ National Mission for Sustaining the Himalayan Ecosystem
- ✚ National Mission for a Green India
- ✚ National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture
- ✚ National Mission on Strategic Knowledge for Climate Change. (Byravan & Rajan, 2013)

The Principles of NAPCC are:

- ✚ Protecting the poor with a sustainable development strategy that considers climate change.

- ✚ Reaching goals for national growth and reducing poverty while protecting the environment.
- ✚ Strategies for managing end-use demand that are effective and cheap.
- ✚ Widespread and speedy use of the right technologies for adaptation and reduction.
- ✚ New and different market, regulatory, and voluntary tools are needed for sustainable development.
- ✚ Effective implementation through unique connections with civil society, local governments, and public-private partnerships. (*Climate Change Programme / Department of Science & Technology, n.d.*)

The Linkage of NAPCC in 2014

Under Prime Minister Narendra Modi, the National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC) has seen significant advancements and expansions. The Modi government has placed a strong emphasis on renewable energy, particularly solar power. The National Solar Mission, one of the eight missions under NAPCC, saw its targets revised upwards to 100 GW by 2022.

The government has also focused on international cooperation and technological deployment to combat climate change. India has been actively participating in global climate summits and has committed to reducing its carbon emissions intensity.

Additionally, the Modi government has launched several schemes to promote solar power and reduce dependency on traditional power sources. One such scheme is the Kisan Urja Suraksha Evam Uthhan Mahabhiyan (KUSUM), which aims to install off-grid solar pumps in rural areas. (National Action Plan on Climate Change, n.d.)

A report from WION says that if the right steps aren't taken, climate change will kill almost 80 million people in 80 years. India has done a lot to stop and manage climate change, which affects the whole world.(WION, n.d.) India, which has the most people, is on the edge of natural disasters caused by global warming. Many things have been done because Prime Minister Narendra Modi has been in charge. For example,

A. International Solar Alliance (ISA)

A project to develop solar power with help from France. It was started in 2015 as a group of "sunshine countries" with the goal of making better use of solar energy. The alliance was made with the goal of using fewer fossil fuels and other energy sources that can't be used again. (*International Solar Alliance*, n.d.)

B. "One Sun, One World, One Grid" Project along with the United Kingdom

The idea behind OSOWOG is to build and expand inter-regional energy grids so that solar energy can be shared around the world. It could be the answer to most of our energy problems around the world. (TIMESOFINDIA.COM, 2021)

C. Swachh Bharat Mission

The all-inclusive programme focused on keeping India and its cities and villages clean by giving every home a toilet. (*Swachh Bharat Mission - Gramin, Department of Drinking Water and Sanitation*, n.d.)

D. COP26 Glasgow Summit:

Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi's biggest and most important move on behalf of India;

- A. To get India's energy capacity from sources other than fossil fuels to 500 GW by 2030.
- B. To cut India's carbon intensity by more than 45% by 2030.
- C. India would reach its goal of emitting net-zero carbon by 2070.

All of these things show that India is doing a great job moving the country and the rest of the world forward. (Team, n.d.)

Panchamrat

Prime Minister Narendra Modi put up a five-pronged plan on the first day of the international climate conference in Glasgow (CoP26) to assist the world get closer to a rise in temperature of 1.5 degrees Celsius. The prime minister's proposal was euphemistically referred to as "Panchamrita," which means "five ambrosia" in Sanskrit. A traditional concoction of milk, ghee, curd, honey, and jaggery is known as panchamrita. These are used in religious rites of the Jain and Hindu

faiths. It is also used as a method in Ayurveda. Ayurveda uses it. (CoP26: Modi Offers 'Panchamrita' Concoction for Climate Conundrum at Glasgow, n.d.)

4. Saudi Vision 2030

Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman gave the first details of Saudi's Energy Vision Plan on April 25, 2016. (Sedra, 2019) The Council of Ministers has assigned the Council of Economic and Development Affairs (CEDA) the responsibility of determining and keeping track of the processes and measures essential to fulfilling "Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030. (Saudi Vision 2030, n.d.) Vision 2030 is an ambitious reform programme with a long-term goal of strengthening the country's fiscal condition and diversifying its economy in more economically reduced oil prices. The policy gives opportunities for multinational corporations to invest in the country, notably in non-oil industries. Saudi Vision 2030 outlines diversification and competitiveness enhancement goals. It is structured around three major topics that outline particular objectives to be attained by 2030. (Sedra, 2019)

- **A thriving society** characterised by urbanisation, culture and entertainment, sports, Umrah, UNESCO World Heritage Sites, and high life expectancy.
- **A booming economy** by employment, women in the workforce, international competitiveness, the Public Investment Fund, foreign direct investment, and exports of non-oil products
- **A nation with aspirations** of non-oil revenues, government efficiency, e-government, household savings and income, non-profits, and volunteerism.

The focus on Saudi Aramco's plan to privatise at least five per cent of its business has received a lot of attention. However, this has taken away from the bigger picture of Vision 2030 and how it is trying to change the country's economy. The government adopted the vision of the world's largest oil conglomerate, which is responsible for about 12 per cent of global oil production. (Petroff, 2016) In a March 2016 interview, Crown Prince Mohammed Bin Salman, who is seen by many as the main architect behind Vision 2030, talked about the plan for the first time. The plan is not without problems, but if it works, it will open up much of the

Saudi economy to foreign investors. This brief looks at why this change is happening, what reforms have already been made, what problems the government is facing, how much USD 2 trillion is planned for creating a new economy, and some of the opportunities that lie ahead. The fund is owned by the government. Saudi dependency on oil-

Table4.1: Oil revenue and non-oil revenue, 1992-2022 in Saudi Riyals

Source: Ministry of Finance, KSA.(Ministry of Finance, n.d.)

Projects of Saudi Vision 2030

Since Saudi Arabia announced its Vision 2030 plan, almost \$1 trillion worth of development projects have started or been announced (This is only one-third of the total amount that is planned to be spent). According to Knight Frank, Saudi Arabia's big Vision 2030 plan for changing the country has so far led to almost \$1 trillion worth of infrastructure and real estate projects all over the country. The global property consultancy also says that the \$1 trillion figure, which is led by a \$575 billion investment to turn the Red Sea Coast into a global tourism and business hub, is only about one-third of what is planned to be spent.(Saudi & Middle East Green Initiatives, n.d.)

According to Faisal Durrani, head of Middle East Research at Knight Frank “The number and value of mega projects around the country, all of which are huge, are set to change the country's real estate landscape, the

standard of living, lifestyle offerings, and perhaps most importantly, show the world the Kingdom's vision for an ultramodern future." "The goals that Vision 2030 is based on are becoming a reality." (*Research: Publications and Reports | Knight Frank Saudi Arabia, n.d.*)

Table 4.2: Major Projects of Saudi Vision 2030

Project	Area Occupied	Date of announcement	Expected Completion	Cost
New Taif project	1,250 km ²	1 March 2017	2020	\$3 billion
Diriyah Gate project	1.5 km ²	20 July 2017	2030	Unknown
Al-Qiddiya project (Al-Qiddiya, south-west of Riyadh)	334 km ²	8 April 2017	2022	\$2.7 billion
Al-Faisaliah project (West of Makkah)	2,450 km ²	26 July 2017	1 st Phase will be completed by the end of 2020	Unknown
Downtown Jeddah	5.2 km ²	27 September 2017	1 st phase will be completed by the end of 2022	\$4.8 billion
NEOM (Tabuk)	26,500 km ²	24 October 2017	1 st Phase will be completed by the end of 2025	\$500 billion
Renewable Energy Project	Unknown	27 March 2018	2030	\$200 billion
Amaala Project Along the Red Sea	3,800 km ²	26 September 2018	1 st phase by the end of 2020	Unknown
King Salman Energy Park Between Dammam and Al-Ahsa	50 km ²	5 December 2018	1 st phase by the end of 2021	\$1.6 billion
Al-'Ula Vision	22,500	11 February	2030	Unknown

	km ²	2019		
King Salman Park, Sports Boulevard, Green Riyadh, and Riyadh Art	>149 km ²	19 March 2019	Unknown	\$23 billion
Great Mosque of Mecca	0.250000 km ²	2017	Mid-2018	\$21.3 billion
Mall of Saudi	8.666000 km ²	2017	2022	\$3.2 billion
The Red Sea Project	28,000 km ²	2018	1 st Phase by the end of 2022	\$3.2 - \$3.7 billion

Sources- The Progress & Achievements of Saudi Arabia, Vision 2030, Vision 2030 Projects

Saudi Arabia Net Zero by 2060

During the inaugural *Saudi Green Initiative Forum*, the official Statement of Kingdom of Saudi Arabia stated that it intends to achieve carbon neutrality by 2060. Implementing the Carbon Circular Economy, based on zero waste, will assist Saudi Arabia in achieving its goal of reducing carbon emissions by 278 million tonnes annually by 2030. As part of its commitment to achieving a cleaner, greener future, the Kingdom will join the **Global Methane Pledge** to help reduce global methane emissions 30% by 2030. In addition, by 2030, the Kingdom will plant 450 million trees and repair 8 million hectares of damaged land, cutting carbon emissions by 200 million tonnes, with more efforts to be revealed in the years ahead. (*Wayback Machine*, n.d.)

5. Current situations of renewable energy in Saudi Arabia

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia aspires to reach 27.3 GW of renewable power capacity by 2023, including 20 GW of solar photovoltaic (PV) and 7 GW of wind power, and 58.7 GW by 2030, with solar accounting for 40 GW at the end of the decade. These goals are part of Saudi Vision 2030. However, according to Global Data, Saudi Arabia won't even come close to achieving the short-term objective if it keeps deploying just 0.1 GW annually, which is its average for the years 2010–2021. In 2023, there will be a 25.8 GW deficit as a result. (*"We Will Be*

Pioneering”: Saudi Arabia Reveals 50% Renewables Goal by 2030, but Is That Realistic?, 2021)

When it comes to renewable energy, the power sector in Saudi Arabia is confronted with various difficulties. Its problems range from a shortage of qualified human resources, excessive bureaucracy, a reliance on desalinated water, and low energy efficiency to low transparency. According to Global Power Analyst Attaurrahman Ojindaram Saibasan, contract enforcement is a challenge the Saudi Government will have to. Needless to mention the nation has a strong insolvency resolution mechanism and is known to handle such projects with accuracy and precision. However, there is a need for the Saudi government to support robust legislation, encourage small-scale installations, and expedite the development of renewable energy sources. (*Saudi Arabia Power Market Size and Trends by Installed Capacity, Generation, Transmission, Distribution and Technology, Regulations, Key Players and Forecast, 2022-2035*, 2023).

6. Current situations of renewable energy in India

India aimed to acquire 40% of its installed electrical capacity from sources other than fossil fuels by November 2021. This goal was originally set for 2030. At COP 21, India committed to achieving this objective as part of its NDCs (Nationally Determined Contributions). (*Renewable Energy in India - Indian Power Industry Investment*, n.d.)

Key Points

A. Renewable Energy in India:

- ✚ As of November 30, 2021, the country's installed capacity for renewable energy (RE) is 150.54 GW (48.55 GW for solar, 40.03 GW for wind, 4.83 GW for small hydro, 10.62 GW for bio-power, and 46.51 GW for large hydro), while its installed capacity for nuclear energy is 6.78 GW.
- ✚ India is the fourth country with the most wind power in the world.
- ✚ This brings the total installed energy capacity from sources other than fossil fuels to 157.32 GW or 40.1% of the total installed electricity capacity of 392.01 GW.

- ✚ India promised at COP26 that it would get 500 GW of electricity from sources other than fossil fuels by 2030. (*Renewable Energy / Make in India*, n.d.)

Further to this India will also have to address the attendant-related issues such as:

- ✚ **Mobilisation of the Necessary Finance:**

Major hurdles include getting the banking sector ready to put up money for higher deployment targets, looking into low-interest, long-term overseas finance, and coming up with a strategy to decrease or share risks by resolving technological and financial constraints.

- ✚ **Land Acquisition:**

Finding land with the potential to be utilised for renewable energy, converting it (if required), obtaining clearance from the Land Ceiling Act, deciding on the land lease rent, obtaining approval from the Revenue Department, and obtaining other permissions might take a significant amount of time. The majority of the land for renewable energy projects has to be purchased by state governments.

- ✚ **Creating Ecosystem:**

Making the country a hub for innovation and manufacturing.

- ✚ **Other:**

Adding more energy from renewable sources to the grid.

Ensuring that power from renewable sources can be relied on and used when needed.

Getting renewable energy into sectors that are thought to be hard to decarbonise. (*Ministry of New and Renewable Energy | Ministry of New and Renewable Energy | India*, n.d.)

7. Assessment of Renewable Energy in India

The Climate Action Tracker (CAT) assesses India's climate objectives and policies as "Highly Insufficient," indicating a misalignment with the 1.5-degree Celsius temperature limit set by the Paris Agreement 2015. Although India's revised Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) has

increased targets on paper, practical emissions reduction is not expected to surpass current efforts. The emissions intensity goal is deemed "Insufficient," an improvement from its earlier rating but still falls short of a fair share contribution. India's conditional NDC is rated "Critically Insufficient" compared to a simulated 1.5°C emissions scenario. Current estimates do not consider the likelihood of higher emissions in 2030 due to historical contributions. In this Scenario India's policies and actions are labelled "Insufficient," projecting emissions of 4.1 to 4.3 GtCO₂e in 2030. The first NDC, focusing on non-fossil fuel capacity and carbon sink creation, is deemed "Critically Inadequate" and requires substantial improvement. The fair-share target is also rated "Insufficient," signifying the need for significant reductions to align with the 1.5-degree Celsius goal. India's fair share rating improved from "Highly Insufficient" to "Insufficient" with the revised NDC. CAT considers the net-zero targets for 2070 "Incomplete target information" by CAT, "emphasizing the need for more details on India's plans for achieving net-zero emissions. (*Ministry of New and Renewable Energy | Ministry of New and Renewable Energy | India, n.d.*)

8. Assessment of Renewable Energy in Saudi Arabia

Climate Action Tracker (CAT) rates Saudi Arabia's climate aims and policies as "Highly inadequate," indicating little to no action and inconsistent with the Paris Agreement's 1.5-degree Celsius target.

Uncertain 2030 Commitment: Saudi Arabia's 2030 climate commitment lacks clarity as baseline data corresponding to its Paris Agreement aim has not been released, resulting in uncertainty regarding its achievement.

Insufficient Policies and Actions: CAT deems Saudi Arabia's policies and initiatives as "Insufficient," suggesting a need for significant improvements by 2030 to align with the Paris Agreement's 1.5°C temperature limit. If adopted globally, the current strategy may lead to global warming exceeding 2°C or even reaching 3°C.

Renewable Energy Goals and Challenges: Saudi Arabia aims to generate 50% of its electricity from renewable sources and 50% from natural gas by 2030. However, concerns exist about the compatibility of this goal with earlier targets and the potential reliance on natural gas, which needs renewed policy alignment with Paris Agreement goals.

Green Initiative and Afforestation Plans: Saudi Arabia's Green Initiative includes plans to plant 450 million trees by 2030. However, uncertainties surround the feasibility of raising the forestry sink to 200 MtCO_{2e}, given the limited forest cover and previous afforestation efforts.

Domestic Target Critique: CAT rates Saudi Arabia's projected 2030 reduction targets as "Highly Insufficient" concerning domestic pathways. The domestic objective is expected to result in rising emissions, inconsistent with the 1.5°C limit.

Critically Insufficient Fair Share Target: Saudi Arabia's Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) is labelled "Critically Insufficient," indicating little to no action in line with the 1.5°C temperature limit. The adoption of Saudi Arabia's strategy globally could lead to temperatures exceeding 4°C.

Insufficient Information on Net Zero Target: Saudi Arabia's Net Zero Goal for 2060 lacks clarity, especially regarding whether it addresses all greenhouse gases and the contribution of land use and forestry sinks. Insufficient information hinders a comprehensive understanding of the net zero target.

Graph 8.1

Renewable Power Capacity, Saudi Arabia Current Forecast vs. Target 2023 and 2030

Source- Global Data Power Intelligence Centre

Ambition Gap

According to Saudi Arabia's conditional NDC, GHG emissions, excluding LULUCF, will rise by 35-72% over 2015 levels by 2030, reaching 861-1105 MtCO₂e/yr.

Saudi Arabia hopes to reduce CO₂ emissions by as much as 130 MtCO₂e/yr (132 MtCO₂e/yr in AR4 GWPs) every year by 2030 by aiding in economic diversification and adopting adaption strategies that also have mitigation co-benefits. This results in 860-1120 MtCO₂e/yr emissions, excluding LULUCF, a rise of 35-72% above 2015 levels, in 2030. (*India*, n.d.)

In comparison, Saudi Arabia's emissions would be reduced by 39–51%, or 31–388 MtCO₂e/yr, below 2015 levels by 2030 under a 1.5°C compatible scenario.

Given the significant contribution of Saudi Arabia's energy sector to its overall emissions profile, this sector will need to account for the majority of emissions reductions, followed by waste management and industrial processes. By 2030, GHG emissions are expected to reach 933–1035 MtCO₂e/yr, a 46–62% rise over 2015 levels under the policies in place at the time.

Long-term plan

At a summit in Riyadh in January 2021, the Saudi Arabian government declared its intention to attain carbon neutrality, which is understood to mean net zero CO₂ emissions. There haven't been any official communications in response to this yet.

When omitting the contribution of LULUCF sinks, Saudi Arabia would need to reduce its GHG emissions by 85% below 2015 levels to reach 97 MtCO₂e/yr by 2050 in order to be 1.5°C compatible. At 93% below 2015 levels, CO₂ emissions should be reduced even more, to 36 MtCO₂yr.¹⁰ (Ltd., 2022)

Graph 8.2: Saudi Arabia's total GHG emissions

Source- 1.5°C National pathway explorer (1.5°C National Pathway Explorer — Saudi Arabia, n.d.)

These positive residual emissions will need to be offset by negative emissions produced by technology advancements, land sinks, or carbon dioxide removal (CDR) strategies. Strict and ambitious policies therefore would be needed in areas including oil and gas exploration, industry, transportation, and power. (*1.5°C National Pathway Explorer — Saudi Arabia, n.d.-b*)

9 Conclusion

India successfully achieved its target of obtaining 40% of its electricity from non-fossil fuel sources by November 2021. As part of the "Paris Agreement on climate change," India aims to reduce its Greenhouse Gas Emissions (GHGe) by 33–35% compared to its 2005 levels by 2030. While India has made significant efforts, the Climate Action Tracker (CAT) deems these efforts insufficient, suggesting that the progress towards the Paris Agreement goals remains inadequate. Although India has made improvements, especially considering its historical emissions, there is a recognised need for further efforts in this direction. In contrast, Saudi Arabia fell short of its goal, achieving less than 1% of its

electricity from non-fossil fuel sources by November 2021. Similar to India, Saudi Arabia has committed to reducing its GHGe under the Paris Agreement. However, CAT highlights Saudi Arabia's lack of substantial efforts, describing them as highly insufficient. Progress toward meeting the Paris Agreement objectives is deemed highly inadequate for Saudi Arabia. The country faces challenges due to the absence of effective policy implementation, and concerted efforts are imperative for Saudi Arabia to align with its commitments to address climate change effectively.

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